

Applications of LLMs and Knowledge Graphs in Healthcare

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 - Knowledge-driven AI application in various domains including Healthcare

Introduction

- Healthcare faces an explosion of scientific data: clinical trials, patient records, research papers.
- Traditional methods struggle to keep pace with this volume and complexity.

Research Question

“How to leverage Large Language Models (LLM) and Knowledge Graphs (KG) in Healthcare?”

LLM+KG in Healthcare

- **LLMs:**
 - Automate information extraction from vast text
 - Summarize complex medical concepts
 - Accelerate research by identifying key findings and patterns
- **Knowledge Graphs:**
 - Reveal hidden connections and patterns within medical data.
 - Enhance explainability, allowing clinicians to understand the reasoning behind AI-driven decisions.
 - Enable question answering like: "What factors influenced the LLM's decision?"

Applications of LLM+KG in Healthcare

- **Extracting Adverse Drug Events from Electronic Health Records**
 - Electronic Health Records (EHRs) contain a wealth of information about patient health, which is often buried in unstructured text, making it difficult to analyze and utilize for research or clinical decision-making.
 - Example: a deep learning framework that combines KGs and pre-trained LLMs to predict drug-drug interactions (DDIs)¹.

¹Xu C, Bulusu KC, Pan H, Elemento O. DDI-GPT: Explainable Prediction of Drug-Drug Interactions using Large Language Models enhanced with Knowledge Graphs. *bioRxiv [Preprint]*. 2024 Dec 9:2024.12.06.627266. doi: 10.1101/2024.12.06.627266. PMID: 39713430; PMCID: PMC11661079.

LLM+KG in Drug-Drug Interaction

Using BioKG for sentence enrichment

¹Xu C, Bulusu KC, Pan H, Elemento O. DDI-GPT: Explainable Prediction of Drug-Drug Interactions using Large Language Models enhanced with Knowledge Graphs. *bioRxiv [Preprint]*. 2024 Dec 9:2024.12.06.627266. doi: 10.1101/2024.12.06.627266. PMID: 39713430; PMCID: PMC11661079.

LLM+KG for DDI: Example

- *Doctor's Note: "Patient was prescribed **ibuprofen** for pain relief. After three days, they developed **gastric bleeding**, requiring discontinuation of the medication."*
- Using **Named Entity Recognition (NER)**, the LLM identifies:
 - **Drug:** Ibuprofen
 - **Adverse Event:** Gastric bleeding
 - **Temporal Relation:** "After three days" (suggesting causality)
- The **KG** contains known relationships:
 - **Ibuprofen** → **Can Cause** → **Gastrointestinal Bleeding** (from medical databases like **DrugBank**, **SIDER**, or **FDA reports**)
 - The KG cross-references *patient history*, checking for risk factors like pre-existing ulcers.
- The system generates an alert:
"Potential Adverse Drug Event detected: Ibuprofen is associated with gastric bleeding in this patient. Consider alternative pain management."

Classifying Medical Misinformation

- Example: Using biomedical knowledge graphs to screen medical LLM outputs

Using KG to detect the misinformation

Alber, D.A., Yang, Z., Alyakin, A. et al. Medical large language models are vulnerable to data-poisoning attacks. *Nat Med* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03445-1>

Classifying Medical Misinformation: Example

- *Tweet/Post: "COVID-19 vaccines contain microchips for government tracking!"*
- Using NER and Relation Extraction, the LLM identifies:
 - **Topic:** COVID-19 vaccine
 - **Claim:** Contains microchips
 - **Sentiment:** Fear-based
 - **Source:** Social media post
- The KG has structured facts:
 - **COVID-19 Vaccine** → **Composition** → **mRNA, Lipid Nanoparticles, Stabilizers** (from CDC, WHO)
 - **Microchips** → **No Relation** → **COVID-19 Vaccines** (not present in validated sources)
- The KG **finds no evidence** supporting the claim and flags it as misinformation.
- The system classifies the claim under **"Conspiracy Theory"** and provides an explanation:

"Scientific evidence from WHO and CDC confirms that COVID-19 vaccines do not contain microchips. This claim is misinformation."

Predicting Patient Risk Prediction

- KG can be used for extracting knowledge from LLMs and external biomedical databases for predicting:
 - the risks for patients
 - patient mortality
 - readmission rates
 - length of hospital stay, and
 - drug recommendations.

Predicting Patient Risk Prediction

Sun, K., Zhang, W., Xu, L., Shen, Y., & Sun, J. (2023). GraphCare: Enhancing Healthcare Predictions with Personalized Knowledge Graphs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.12788*. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.12788>

Predicting Patient Risk Prediction

*Doctor's Note: "The patient, a 68-year-old male with **diabetes and hypertension**, developed a **fever (38.9°C)**, **elevated heart rate (110 bpm)**, and **low blood pressure (90/60 mmHg)** after surgery. Blood tests show elevated **white blood cell count and lactate levels.**"*

Using ER and Temporal Analysis, the LLM identifies:

- **Patient Risk Factors:** Diabetes, hypertension
- **Vital Signs:** Fever, high heart rate, low blood pressure
- **Lab Findings:** Elevated WBC, high lactate (indicators of infection and shock)
- **Temporal Context:** Post-surgical condition

The KG has structured medical facts:

- **Sepsis Risk Factors** → Include → **Fever, Hypotension, High Lactate, Infection Signs**
- **Diabetes & Hypertension** → Increase Susceptibility → **Severe Infections**
- **Early Interventions** → Include → **IV fluids, Broad-Spectrum Antibiotics, ICU Monitoring**

The system generates an alert:

"Patient at high risk of sepsis. Recommend immediate IV fluids, blood cultures, and ICU monitoring."

Extracting Proteins Interactions from Research Papers

- **LLMs:** Process unstructured research papers to identify proteins, interactions, and biological contexts using Natural Language Processing (NLP).
- **KGs:** Validate, integrate, and link extracted interactions with existing biomedical databases (STRING, BioGRID, IntAct).

Excerpt from a study on breast cancer:

*"Our experiments demonstrate that **BRCA1 interacts with p53**, leading to enhanced tumor suppression. Furthermore, we observed that BRCA1 forms a complex with RAD51, facilitating DNA repair."*

A knowledge graph for healthcare

NER (Extraction):

- **Proteins:** BRCA1, p53, RAD51
- **Interactions:**
 - **BRCA1** → **interacts with** → **p53** (Tumor Suppression)
 - **BRCA1** → **forms complex with** → **RAD51** (DNA Repair)

The KG cross-references biomedical databases (integration):

- **BRCA1** → **Known Interactions** → **p53 (Tumor Suppression)**
- **BRCA1** → **Known Interactions** → **RAD51 (DNA Repair Pathway)**
- **New Findings?** If an extracted interaction is novel (not in STRING or BioGRID), it is flagged for further review.

Protein 1	Interaction Type	Protein 2	Biological Context	Source
BRCA1	Interacts with	p53	Tumor Suppression	Research Paper
BRCA1	Forms complex with	RAD51	DNA Repair	Research Paper

LLM Extraction Methods

While NER is a powerful method for extracting **drugs, symptoms, and adverse events**, other **LLM-based approaches** can further improve ADE detection:

1. **Relation Extraction (RE)** – Identifies **cause-effect** relationships between drugs and adverse effects.
2. **Zero-Shot/Few-Shot Learning** – Enables ADE detection **without extensive labeled data**.
3. **Prompt Engineering** – Uses **structured prompts** to extract and summarize ADEs.
4. **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** – Integrates external medical databases (e.g., FAERS, DrugBank) with LLM responses.
5. **Fine-Tuned Models** – Tailored LLMs for **clinical text analysis** (e.g., BioBERT, MedGPT).

How LLM+KG help healthcare?

- **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG):** diagnostic predictions and clinical decision support, LLM+KG provide accurate and contextually relevant information.
- **Knowledge Graph Construction and Completion:** LLMs assist in building and enriching KGs by extracting entities and relationships from unstructured medical texts.
- **Question Answering (QA) Systems:** Combining LLMs with KGs enhances medical QA systems by providing precise and contextually relevant answers.
- **Information Extraction and Entity Linking:** LLMs, integrated with KGs, improve the extraction of medical information by accurately identifying and linking entities within medical texts.

Current Research

- **Following a LLM+KG approach to identify adverse drug events based on personal information of patients:**
 - Gathering the source data (disease, drugs, protein, patients, genes, etc.)
 - Extract the important entities and relationships using relation extraction method
 - Constructing a KG
 - Predicting the adverse drug reaction events based on patient information (i.e. demographic data)

PrimeKG: A Precision Medicine-oriented KG

20 high-quality resources

17,080 diseases

4M relationships

drug-disease prediction

enable multi-modal analyses based on text descriptions of clinical guidelines and KG structure.

- Disease-drug indications
- Disease-drug contraindications
- Disease-drug off-label use
- Disease-phenotype associations (+/-)
- Disease-disease associations
- Disease-protein associations
- Disease-exposure associations

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A spectrum of developmental disorders that includes autism, and Asperger syndrome. Signs and symptoms include poor communication skills, defective social interactions, and repetitive behaviors. Each child with autism spectrum disorder is likely to have a unique pattern of behavior [...] Autism spectrum disorder has no single known cause. [...] Autism spectrum disorder affects children of all races and nationalities, but certain factors increase a child's risk [...] There's no way to prevent autism spectrum disorder, but there are treatment options.

Risperidone is a second-generation antipsychotic (SGA) medication used in the treatment of a number of mood and mental health conditions including schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. The half-life is 3 hours in extensive metabolizers. Though its precise mechanism of action is not fully understood, current focus is on the ability of risperidone to inhibit the D2 dopaminergic receptors and 5-HT2A serotonergic receptors in the brain. [...] Risperidone and its active metabolite, 9-hydroxyrisperidone, are ~88% and ~77% protein-bound in human plasma, respectively. [...] The primary action of risperidone is to decrease dopaminergic and serotonergic pathway activity in the brain, therefore decreasing symptoms of schizophrenia and mood disorders.

Chandak, P., Huang, K., & Zitnik, M. (2023). Building a knowledge graph to enable precision medicine. *Scientific Data*, 10(1), 67.

Thank you

Questions?

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